

1 **Traversing the Permian-Triassic threshold: Insights from the dolomite of the**
2 **Velebit Mountain, External Dinarides, Croatia**

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19

20 **Abstract:** The Permian-Triassic boundary (PTB) strata records a major transformative event in
21 Earth's history, characterized by extreme climatic perturbations and a drastic alteration in ocean
22 and atmosphere system dynamics, culminating in the most devastating mass extinction of the
23 Phanerozoic. A notable shift from skeletal to microbial carbonate production marks this

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1 boundary. Whereas many studies have explored the End-Permian Mass extinction (EPME) in
2 marine and terrestrial realms, the record of this transition within shallow lagoonal and peritidal
3 deposits of platforms remain scarcely investigated. These settings, pose challenges due to the
4 scarcity of dating possibilities and high sensitivity to diagenetic processes. This study
5 investigates the PTB strata at the Brušane-Sy section in Croatia's External Dinarides, focusing on
6 a continuous, mostly fabric-preserving dolomite succession. Utilizing high-resolution
7 petrography, biostratigraphy (conodonts and foraminifers), and chemostratigraphy ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$), we
8 delineate the sedimentary responses and textural changes across the boundary. The Late Permian
9 fine-crystalline dolostone represents well preserved cryptomicrobial, inter- and supra-, and
10 subtidal lagoonal mudstone, wackestone, and packstone microfacies with well-preserved
11 calcareous algae, foraminifers, and other organisms. Geopetal textures suggest stages of
12 subaerial exposure with vadose to freshwater-influenced mixing-zone diagenesis. Conversely,
13 the Triassic dolostone, containing the *Hindeoudus parvus* conodont, encompass a sharp
14 transition to a medium-crystalline, fabric destructive dolomite texture. The transition between
15 this preserving Permian to the Triassic medium-coarse crystalline texture, can be explained by
16 two distinct dolomitization processes. Firstly, the transgression during the Early Triassic that
17 facilitated the redeposition of aragonite/high Mg-calcite loose crystals, acting as precursors for
18 the growth of medium/coarse dolomite crystals. Secondly, early diagenesis dolomitization
19 influenced by the mixing of isotopically contrasting dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) fluids.
20 This condition was further impacted by substantial methane generation resulting from the mass
21 extinction event. Both hypotheses could explain the reduced negative excursion in $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ seen
22 in Brušane-Sy which normally marks the end-Permian extinction.

23

1 **Keywords:** Dolomitization, microbial carbonate, diagenesis, extinction, platform

2

3 **INTRODUCTION**

4 The catastrophic events at the End-Permian Mass Extinction (EPME) event triggered the most
5 profound biodiversity crisis of the Phanerozoic (Sepkoski, 2002; Payne & Clapham, 2012; Penn
6 *et al.*, 2018). This event resulted in substantial loss of both marine and terrestrial species,
7 accompanied by significant alterations of ecosystem dynamics and biogeochemical cycles (e.g.
8 Jurikova *et al.*, 2020; Dal Corso *et al.*, 2022, Wignall & Bond, 2023). Numerous calcifying
9 species of calcareous algae, foraminifers, sponges, and corals among others vanished during this
10 period (Song *et al.*, 2013; Stanley, 2016). This biodiversity crisis transcended far beyond mere
11 species extinction as it significantly altered features of deposits on continental margins, replacing
12 Paleozoic skeletal carbonate depositional systems with extensive Early Triassic microbial-
13 dominated ones (Schubert & Bottjer, 1992; Baud *et al.*, 1997, 2005; 2007; Pruss & Bottjer, 2004;
14 Sheehan & Harris, 2004; Woods 2014; Yao *et al.*, 2016). Numerous studies have explored the
15 impact of the EPME events across varied sedimentary settings, but mainly the open marine and
16 terrestrial environments. Within carbonate depositional systems, the chronology of events and
17 their repercussions have been extensively documented across a number of discrete
18 paleogeographic locales including: (1) open marine carbonate slope and basinal facies (e.g.
19 Lehrmann *et al.*, 1998; Yin *et al.*, 2001; Richoz *et al.*, 2010; Friesenbichler *et al.*, 2018; Gliwa, *et*
20 *al.*, 2020); (2) mixed carbonate-siliciclastic ramps (e.g. Haas *et al.*, 1995; 2007; Farabegoli *et al.*,
21 2007; Kolar-Jurkovšek *et al.*, 2011; Aljinović *et al.*, 2018) (3) isolated carbonate platforms (e.g.
22 Lehrmann *et al.*, 2015; Bagherpour *et al.*, 2017; Richoz *et al.*, 2014); and (4) large carbonate

1 platforms (e.g. Lehrmann *et al.*, 2001, Krystyn *et al.*, 2003; Richoz *et al.*, 2010; Kershaw *et al.*,
2 2012; Heindel *et al.*, 2018).

3 All these studies have significantly enriched the understanding of the events marking the
4 Permian-Triassic boundary (PTB) strata. However, a research gap persists concerning shallow
5 lagoonal and peritidal zones of platforms. This is probably because such deposits were often
6 subjected to pervasive dolomitization which presents a challenge for accurate biostratigraphic
7 dating, thereby hindering a comprehensive understanding of their responses to EPME
8 perturbations. Whereas some sections similar to those settings of interest have been described
9 (Farabegoli & Perri 2012; Brandner *et al.*, 2012; Clarkson *et al.*, 2013, 2015; Eltom *et al.*, 2016),
10 a precise description of microfacies changes through the boundary is still missing. This study
11 aims at bridging the research gap by presenting a detailed examination of a continuous dolostone
12 section through the EPME interval at the Brušane-Sy section in Croatia.

13 In Croatia, the Permian-Triassic (Wordian-Griesbachian) carbonate platform deposits
14 within the Velebit Formation (Velebit Mts., External Dinarides) are primarily comprised of
15 dolostone and subordinate limestone with a thickness exceeding 900 meters (Fig.2) (Salopek,
16 1942; Kochansky-Devidé, 1979; 1982; Flügel, 1977). During the Permian, the platform was
17 situated on the western margin of the Palaeotethys, near the paleo-equator (Sremac, 2005), and
18 developed over topographic highs (horsts), separated from the carbonate platform developed in
19 the Southern Alps by major inter-platform graben basins (Sremac, 2005; Aljinović *et al.* 2008;
20 Aljinović & Isozaki, 2010). As a result, the Velebit Fm. represents very shallow lagoonal to
21 sabkha-type sedimentation devoid of direct terrigenous influences, which is in contrast with
22 other coeval very shallow carbonate dominated sections (Farabegoli & Perri 2012; Brandner *et*
23 *al.*, 2012; Eltom *et al.*, 2016).

1 The Brušane-Sy section has a variety of microfacies and petrographic features through
2 the EPME interval, recording the unique environmental variations of the isolated platform
3 interior (subtidal facies) and its margins (intertidal/supratidal facies). By implementing a multi-
4 stratigraphic approach, encompassing biostratigraphy focused on foraminifers and conodonts,
5 and carbon isotopes, the chronological contours of the EPME were meticulously traced, placing
6 the observed microfacies transitions within a temporal reference framework.

7 An important finding in the Brušane-Sy section is the remarkable divergence of dolomite
8 fabrics across the boundary, indicating exceptional dolomitizing depositional circumstances
9 reflecting near surface to shallow burial diagenetic conditions. Accordingly, in addition to
10 describing the paleoenvironmental transition, herein the study is focused on the processes that
11 define the genesis of a medium crystalline dolomite microtexture at the base of the Early Triassic
12 that conformably lies in sharp contact with fine-crystalline and fabric-preserving dolomitized
13 Late Permian facies. Through a detailed microfacies examination, this study aims to enrich the
14 broader understanding of the generalized EPME's sedimentological and ecological evolution,
15 shedding light on the intricate sedimentary conditions controlled by sea-level fluctuation during
16 the PTB interval within a scarcely explored isolated carbonate platform developed at the western
17 Palaeotethys.

18

19 **GEOLOGICAL SETTING**

20 The Permian-Triassic boundary section presented herein is located near the village of Brušane, in
21 the Velebit Mountains (44°29'56'' N; 15°15'13'' E; Fig. 1). Earlier studies on the PTB in the
22 Velebit Mts. are outlined in Sremac (2005) and Fio *et al.* (2010). Extending for about 150 km,
23 the Velebit Mts. form part of the External Dinarides tectonic belt—also referred to as the High

1 Karst Zone by Schmidt *et al.* (2008). This belt stretches along the northern periphery of the
2 Adriatic Sea, bridging the Southern Alps in Austria and Italy to the Albanides and Hellenides
3 (Fig. 1). The mountains are made up of multiple sequences of tectonized rocks ranging from
4 Carboniferous to Neogene. The lithologies composing this tectonic belt recorded the Late
5 Palaeozoic-Triassic rifting of the Gondwana margin (Vlahović *et al.*, 2005), later inheriting
6 imprints from Mesozoic-Cenozoic convergent tectonics through the closure of the Palaeotethys
7 and then subduction along the Neotethys northern margin (van Hinsenberg *et al.*, 2020). The
8 part of this geological belt comprising Mesozoic and Paleogene platform carbonate rocks is
9 called the Adriatic Carbonate Platform (Vlahović *et al.*, 2005).

10 Palaeozoic and Early Triassic rocks are among the better preserved successions in the Velebit
11 Mts. Particularly, Carboniferous and Permian sedimentary rocks constitute the core of the
12 prominent Brušane anticline (Salopek, 1942; Sokač *et al.*, 1974; 1976; Figure 1). The
13 Carboniferous contains mainly siliclastic deposits whereas the Permian is characterised by mixed
14 clastic-carbonate successions (Vlahović *et al.*, 2005). These encompasses three distinct
15 stratigraphic units, in ascending order (Salopek, 1942; Flügel, 1977; Kochansky- Devidé, 1979;
16 1982): (i) the Sakmarian (Cisuralian) Rattendorf Beds (carbonates), the proposed (ii) Artinskian
17 (Cisuralian) clastic Košna formation, and the (iii) Late Cisuralian-Lopingian carbonate Velebit
18 Fm. (Fig. 2). Previous studies (Flügel, 1977; Kiessling *et al.*, 2003; Sremac, 2005; Aljinović *et*
19 *al.*, 2008) show that these sediments were deposited in an epeiric sea during the Carboniferous to
20 Early Permian period along northern Gondwana (Vlahović *et al.*, 2005), hosting shallow-marine
21 carbonate (Rattendorf Beds) and terrigenous clastic rocks (Košna formation). In the late Early
22 Permian, this platform was affected by rift-related extensional tectonism which created several

1 horsts and grabens. The Velebit Fm. probably developed on one of few Permian topographic
2 highs (horsts) (Aljinović *et al.*, 2008; Aljinović & Isozaki, 2010).

3 The Velebit Formation was initially proposed as an informal unit by Flügel (1977, p. 315),
4 and later referenced by Sremac (1991, 2005) and Aljinović *et al.* (2008), albeit without formal
5 recognition. It is a ~900 m thick succession dominated by dolostone, interspersed with three
6 lenticular limestone intervals: lower, middle, and upper (Salopek, 1942; Kochansky-Devidé,
7 1965; 1979; 1982) as shown in Figure 2. These limestone segments contain abundant marine
8 fauna including gastropods, bivalves, brachiopods, cephalopods, rugose coral, sponges,
9 bryozoans, fusulinids, smaller foraminifers, and calcareous algae, all essentially being Tethyan
10 elements. The biostratigraphic subdivision of these intervals is based on three fusulinid
11 assemblage zones in ascending order: the *Eoverbeekina salopeki* Zone, *Neoschwagerina*
12 *craticulifera* Zone, and *Yabeina syrtalis* Zone (Kochansky-Devide, 1965), presently correlated
13 with the Artinskian (Late Cisuralian), Wordian or Murgabian (early Midian; middle
14 Guadalupian) and Capitanian (or middle–late Midian; late Guadalupian), respectively (Sremac,
15 1991; 2005; Aljinović *et al.*, 2008). The lithological composition and fossil content reveal
16 deposition in a shallow-marine, warm-water setting—i.e., a carbonate platform (Sremac, 1991;
17 Fio *et al.*, 2010). Whereas the lower limestone interval contains rare macrofossils (nautiloids and
18 gastropods) and microfossils (foraminifers and algae) (Kochansky-Devidé, 1965), the middle
19 limestone interval has a unique association of colonial tabular calcisponges, fenestrate
20 bryozoans, and algae forming patch reefs (Sremac, 1991). However, the absence of reef colonies
21 in the subsequent strata hints at an unrimmed platform during the Late Permian deposition of the
22 Velebit Fm. (Sremac, 1991; Aljinović *et al.*, 2003).

1 The upper limestone interval is conformably overlain by the youngest Permian strata—over
2 300 m of less-fossiliferous, light grey and white dolostone (Fig. 2), which contain sparse
3 calcareous algae, foraminifers, and gastropods. A white dolostone, often referred to as the
4 “transitional dolostone” or “boundary dolostone,” is conformably overlain by dolostone
5 containing a siliciclastic component, termed “sandy dolostone”. This sandy dolostone, Early
6 Triassic in age (Salopek, 1948; Sokač *et al.*, 1974; 1976), is notably devoid of bioclasts.

7 Fio *et al.* (2010) dealt with the positioning of the PTB boundary in the Velebit Mts.
8 employing stable isotope analysis of carbonates ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) and organic matter ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{org}}$)
9 alongside major, trace, and rare earth element (REE) analyses of carbonates. At the Rizvanuša
10 locality (near Brušane), these authors placed the PTB about 5 m above the lithologic boundary
11 transitional dolostone to sandy dolostone following the last occurrence of Permian foraminifers,
12 and a presence of a noticeable negative $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ excursion above it. Based on Fio *et al.* (2010),
13 however, no conspicuous facies changes, characteristic of the PTB, are evident at the Rizvanuša
14 section. Additional geochemical analysis of sediments at the PTB interval by these authors
15 suggested transgressive phases during the late Permian, transitioning into a shallow/stagnant
16 anoxic marine environment as the PT boundary approached. The latter environmental condition
17 persisted into the earliest Triassic.

1

2 **Figure 1.** Geologic map of Croatia and surroundings (modified after Schmidt et al., 2008;) and of the Brušane area
 3 (modified after Salopek, 1942; Kochansky-Devidé, 1982).

4

Figure 2. Simplified stratigraphy of the Permian rocks in the Velebit Mountains with informal foraminifera assemblage zones (after Salopek, 1942; Kochansky-Devidé, 1965; 1979; 1982; Flügel, 1977).

19

20 **METHODS AND MATERIALS**

21 To better understand the Permian-Triassic boundary in the External Dinarides, our study
 22 examined the microfacies, petrographic, biostratigraphic, and chemostratigraphic ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$,
 23 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{carb}}$) aspects of the uppermost Permian and the overlying Lower Triassic dolostone within
 24 the Brušane locality. The 73 m thick Brušane-Sy section was measured along a local forest trail,

1 89 carbonate rock samples were collected for isotopic analyses, 38 for thin sections for
2 microfacies analyses, and 31 for conodont extraction.

3 **Petrography**

4 The thin sections underwent a standard staining process utilizing K-ferricyanide and Alizarin
5 Red S, followed by examination under a polarizing microscope. Scanning Electron Microscopy
6 (SEM) analyses were conducted with JEOL JSM-6510 LV SEM (JEOL, Tokyo, Japan) equipped
7 with an energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscope using Oxford INCA X-act system (Oxford
8 Instruments, High Wycombe, UK) housed at INA d.d., Zagreb, Croatia. The mineralogical size
9 and distribution (e.g dolomite, pyrite framboids) were studied petrographically using both plane
10 polarizing light microscopy and SEM. In addition, a MIRA3GMU field emission scanning
11 electron microscope (TESCAN) was combined with an electron dispersion spectrometer (Oxford
12 Instruments) at Czech Geological Survey, Prague. Imaging proceeded by operating the
13 instrument at 15.0 kV and 17 mm working distance for magnifications ranging from 5000x to
14 30,000x.

15 **XRD analysis**

16 XRD data was collected at Czech Geological Survey, Prague, using a D8 Advance
17 diffractometer equipped with a LYNXEYE XE silicon strip detector (Bruker, Germany). The
18 setup used Bragg–Brentano geometry and CuK1 radiation ($\lambda = 1.54058 \text{ \AA}$). Data was collected in
19 the 2θ range from 4 to 80° , using 0.015° step-size increments, and collection times of 0.8 s per
20 step-size. Rietveld refinement was concluded as implemented in the TOPAS 5 code (Bruker,
21 Germany). Only scale factors, dolomite unit-cell parameters, and size of coherent diffraction
22 domains were refined.

23 **Stable isotopes**

1 Selected micrites were powdered by using a dental micromotor drill (Nouvag NM3000) on a
2 polished surface. Inorganic carbon and oxygen isotopic composition analyses were conducted
3 with a Kiel II automated reaction system associated with a Delta Plus ratio mass spectrometer
4 (Thermo Fisher) at the University of Graz. The powders were reacting with concentrated
5 phosphoric acid at 70°C for 10 minutes. NBS-19 (+1.95 ‰ $\delta^{13}\text{C}$; -2.20 ‰ $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) and an in-house
6 marble (+1.21‰ $\delta^{13}\text{C}$; -7.75‰ $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) were used as standards. The standard deviation σ of the
7 analyses based on repeated standard measurements was ≤ 0.03 ‰ for the reported $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, and ≤ 0.1
8 ‰ for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of organic carbon (OC) in sediments from the PTB defined in this
9 study (see below), were determined using a method involving combustion in an elemental
10 analyzer connected to an IR-MS equipped with a ConFlo IV reference gas unit (Delta V,
11 Thermo-Scientific) at the Czech Geological Survey, Prague. Enough sample mass as to obtain
12 roughly 70 μg of organic carbon was encapsulated in tin (Sn) foil and combusted at 1040 °C. The
13 precision of $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ measurements was maintained above 0.1‰, verified by analyzing NBS-22
14 reference material ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}} = -30.06$ ‰; National Bureau of Standards, USA). The reproducibility
15 for $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ was within ± 0.12 ‰. All data are reported relative to the V-PDB.

16 **Conodont extraction**

17 For conodont extraction, carbonate rock samples, each weighing around 4 kg, were fragmented
18 into smaller chunks (ranging from 3-10 cm^3 in volume). These fragments were then placed in
19 buckets and submerged in a diluted formic acid solution (< 10% by volume), where they
20 remained for a reaction period of 3 to 4 days, or until the formic acid was fully expended. The
21 residues were gathered and sieved using sieving meshes of 1 mm and 64 μm . Grains sizing
22 between 64 μm and 1 mm were collected and dried. These dried residues were then introduced

1 into dissolved sodium tungstate with a density of 2.81 g cm^{-3} . The deposited sedimentary fraction
2 was collected, rinsed, and dried.

3

4 **RESULTS**

5 The microfacies assemblages along the 73 m thick Brušane-Sy section, together with the
6 biostratigraphic data, are compiled in Figure 3. The section consists of decimetre to metre-thick
7 laminar dolostone beds interstratified with structureless (massive) dolostone. A Late Permian age
8 within the first 69.5 m of the Brušane-Sy section is based on foraminifer assemblages. These
9 foraminifers belong to the order Hemigordiopsida, which is a notable indicator of shallower
10 water environment by the end of the Permian in Slovenia (Nestell *et al.*, 2011; Kolar-Jurkovšek
11 *et al.*, 2017), Serbia (Nestell *et al.*, 2009), and Bosnia and Herzegovina (Kolar-Jurkovšek *et al.*,
12 2021). There are some nodosariids and globivalvulinids also present, and in the uppermost part
13 of the interval the finding of fusulinids of the genus *Staffella* points to a Late Permian age for
14 sample Sy-37x (Appendix A1). Five conodont elements, useful for taxonomic identification,
15 were recovered from the overlying bed Sy-37. These conodont elements are identified as
16 *Hindeodus pisai* (Perri & Farabegoli, 2003), *Hindeodus typicalis* (Sweet, 1970), *Hindeodus*
17 *parvus* (Kozur & Pjatakova, 1976). Also, two conodont elements recovered from Sy-38 are
18 identified as *Hindeodus cf. praeparvus* (Kozur) (Appendix A2). The assignment of an Early
19 Triassic age to the uppermost part of the studied succession (ranging from 69.5 m to 73 m) is
20 substantiated by the first appearance of the conodont *Hindeodus parvus* within the upper part of
21 bed 37 (sample Sy-37) (e.g., Jiang *et al.*, 2011).

22 A notable observation is the distinct microtextural variation between the Late Permian
23 part of the section, comprised by a fabric-preserving dolostone and the conformably succeeding

- 1 Early Triassic dolostone within the upper portion of the section (Fig. 3). This topmost dolostone
- 2 is medium crystalline and devoid of foraminiferal or algal components. The textural distinction
- 3 not only marks a significant transitional phase but also provides a clear discernable stratigraphic
- 4 marker.

1

1 **Figure 3.** Lithological profile of the Brušane-Sy section with microfacies and biostratigraphy.

2 **Late Permian microfacies**

3 In the Late Permian part of the succession (0-69.5 m), three predominant types of dolostone
4 microfacies have been identified, namely: (1) dolomudstone, (2) dolowackestone, and (3)
5 dolopackstone. They exhibit allochems and early diagenetic sedimentary structures that are well-
6 preserved and mimically dolomitized. The matrix is fine-crystalline rarely $\geq 2 \mu\text{m}$ in size (Fig 4
7 A-F).

8 *Dolomudstone*

9 The dolomudstone is characterized by the fine-crystalline dolomitic matrix that contains sparse
10 fragmented allochems (mostly gastropod shells) (Fig. 4A). The microfacies frequently exhibit
11 cryptomicrobial laminates (Fig. 4B). The laminated fabric consists of millimetre thick crinkled
12 laminae that differ in internal composition. Finer laminae correspond to relatively homogenous
13 dolomicrite layers. Coarser laminae consist of small peloids ($\leq 0,15 \text{ mm}$) cemented by
14 dolosparite. The laminar couplet resembles cement-filled fenestrae and are thought as remnants
15 of microbial mats. The dolosparite-filled voids sometimes exhibit geopetal structures, suggestive
16 of vadose zone dissolution-reprecipitation. A stromatactis-type fabric was also observed (Fig.
17 4C). Abundant teepees and signs of bioturbation are present, showing subaerial exposure
18 (Goldhammer & Harris, 1989), and low-grade reworking by organisms, respectively (Fig. 4D).
19 Small framboidal pyrite ($\leq 10 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter) appears to be evenly distributed in the dolomicrite
20 (Fig. 4E), whereas coarser pyrite crystals were observed filling-in fenestral cavities, together
21 with dolosparite.

1
2 **Figure 4.** Microphotographs of the Late Permian dolomudstone (A-E). (A) The dolomudstone consists of a fine-
3 grained dolomitic matrix with rare fine fossil detritus or coarser fragments of gastropods (lower left) that are
4 unevenly dispersed in the carbonate mud. Voids of different shapes and sizes filled with fine-grained sediment
5 (crystal silt) at the bottom and coarse crystalline cement in the upper part of the voids are common in dolomudstone,
6 (sample Sy-6); (B) Microbial (stromatolite, bindstone) structure, occasionally form thin interlayers within mudstone

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1 (sample Sy-16b). The fabric consists of millimeter thick micrite laminae and laminae that consist of small peloids
2 and sparitic cement. Small spar-filled cavities (fenestrae) signify decay of microbial organisms; (C) Stromatactoid
3 fabric is evidenced with the elongated voids with flattened bottom and serrated roof (sample Sy-12); (D) Desiccation
4 in mudstone is indicated by disconnected mud-rich laminae and bending of laminae forming tepee structure (sample
5 Sy-16b); (E) Pyrite framboids evenly distributed in the dolomudstone (sample Sy-11); (F) SEM in dolomudstone.
6 Dolomite crystals rarely measure more than 2 μm in size (sample Sy-16a).

7

8 *Dolowackestone/ Dolopackstone*

9 These microfacies consist of abundant and diverse skeletal fragments, and lesser abundances of
10 intraclasts and small peloids within a dolomicritic matrix, forming a wackestone fabric (Fig. 5A)
11 or a tightly packed arrangement in packstone (Fig. 5B). A significant feature of both lithologies
12 is the prevalence of fossils, in particular calcareous algae. Additionally, there are occurrences of
13 organic-walled microfossils, such as acritarchs (Appendix A1). Other fossil fragments include
14 gastropods, foraminifers, bivalves, and ostracods (Figs. 5A, B, D). Some samples reveal
15 cryptomicrobial structures (Demico & Hardie, 1994), exhibiting at times an incrusting nature
16 (Fig. 5C). Calcareous sponges and cyanoids (calcified cyanobacteria) fragments are rare, with
17 various sizes of bioclasts forming occasional faint parallel lamination.

18 The original microfabrics of gastropods, foraminifers, bivalves, and ostracods has been
19 replaced by dolosparite. The gastropod shells are geopetally infilled by dolomicrite (Fig. 5D),
20 mirroring the dolomicrite found in the matrix. Within the microfacies, intraclasts coexist with
21 bioclasts, or, on rare occasions, serve as primary constituents. These intraclasts exhibit irregular,
22 often flattened shapes and are poorly sorted and rounded. In thin section, they appear darker than
23 the adjacent matrix with dimensions ranging from 10 μm to >1 mm (Fig. 5E). Occasionally,
24 intraclasts fill larger cracks or voids, and are encircled by coarse dolomite mosaic cement (Fig.

1 5E). Both wackestone and packstone lithotypes feature numerous millimeter-scale voids. In the
2 lower portions of these voids, silt-sized particles accumulated as a geopetal infill, whereas the
3 remaining voids, made up of dolosparitic mosaic (Fig 5F), hint at dissolution likely occurring
4 under vadose conditions.

5 At least three samples show hardground surfaces, indicating early diagenetic lithification
6 (i.e., samples Sy-11, -21, -33). These hardground surfaces are distinguished by a compositional
7 shift in the primary limy constituents along a sharp boundary cutting through primary
8 components. The abundant fossil content in the dolowackestone/dolopackstone points to subtidal
9 deposition within a low-energy lagoon. Intraclasts in the microfacies would have originated from
10 desiccation and fragmentation of supratidal to intertidal setting supporting microbial mat
11 development, and would have been redeposited later in a nearby lagoon, particularly during
12 storm events. The dolomitization process of wackestone and packstone retained a fair amount of
13 the primary fabrics, with slightly recrystallized foraminiferal shells still allowing genus-level
14 identification. A marginally more altered fabric is seen near the PTB (in samples Sy-34 and Sy-
15 36), with beds depicting a relatively coarser crystalline dolomite texture.

1
 2 **Figure 5.** Microphotographs of Late Permian dolowackstone and dolopackstone. (A) The dolowackstone consists
 3 of abundant skeletal fragments in a micritic matrix. (sample Sy-7); (B) The dolopackstone fabric has tightly packed
 4 skeletal fragments, intraclasts, and small pelloids (sample Sy-28); (C) Incrusting character of the microbial
 5 structures observed in dolowackstone (center of the microphotograph) (sample Sy-4); (D) The most prominent
 6 characteristic of the packstone and wackestone rock types is the presence of calcareous algae and abundance of their

1 spores (small arrows), ostracods and gastropods. The gastropod shells are geopetally infilled by micrite (lower part
2 of the microphotograph grey arrow) (sample Sy-1b). (E) Intraclasts are important constituents of the
3 dolowackestone/dolopackstone. They have irregular, often flattened, shapes and are poorly sorted and rounded
4 (sample Sy-21b); (F) Numerous millimeter-scale voids in wackestone and packstone lithotypes filled with silt-sized
5 particles as a geopetal infill at the bottom, whereas the remaining voids are made up of dolosparitic mosaic (sample
6 Sy-19).

7

8 **Early Triassic microfacies**

9 The base of the Triassic in the Brušane-Sy section is made up of a medium crystalline, fabric-
10 destructive dolostone. Significantly larger subhedral/euhedral crystals (33 - 44 μm – Fig. 6A-D)
11 occur as a polymodal planar-s or planar-e dolomite texture (Sibley & Gregg, 1987). It is
12 important to notice that bed Sy-37 (demarked in Fig. 3) is divided into its lower part (represented
13 by sample Sy 37x) and its upper portion (represented by sample Sy-37) due to the significant
14 differences in textural features and palaeontological content. Sample Sy-37x shows crystalline
15 microtexture, but its fossil content (see below) implies a Permian age. On the contrary, sample
16 Sy-37 exhibits slightly larger crystals forming a sucrosic medium-crystalline microtexture
17 lacking skeletal material. Except for small intraclasts, the primary composition of sample Sy-37
18 is occluded during pervasive dolomitization (Fig. 6A). Bed 38 (i.e., sample Sy-38) represents a
19 relatively coarser unimodal planar-s, planer-e dolomite type, with a scarce presence of fairly
20 rounded simple ooids and microspheres preserved within micritic envelopes (Fig. 6B).
21 Importantly, sample Sy-37 contains ~2% detrital material. Detrital material is represented by
22 irregularly shaped quartz and muscovite, sometimes concentrated in pseudostylolites, whereas
23 sample Sy-38 lacks these detrital components. Patchy distributed small framboids with < 10 μm
24 in diameter were observed in sample Sy-37 (Fig. 6D).

1
2 **Figure 6.** Crystalline Triassic dolostone. (A) Medium to coarse crystalline microtexture of the Early Triassic
3 dolostone with faintly preserved rounded primary components - small intraclasts (sample Sy-37). (B) A faintly
4 preserved spherical forms (oids/microspheres) that consist of one dense dolomicritic envelope and dolosparitic
5 nucleus (sample Sy-38). (C) SEM microphotographs of macrocrystalline dolostone type (sample Sy-38). (D) Small
6 framboids with < 10 μm in diameter were observed in the intraclasts of sample Sy-37.

7

8 **XRD dolomite composition**

9 Detailed XRD analyses into the dolomite composition at the PTB within the Brušane-Sy section
10 revealed distinctive characteristics between Permian and Triassic samples, as presented in Figure
11 7. XRD diffractograms of bulk rock samples Sy-37x (Permian) and Sy-37 (Triassic) showed
12 notable b-type dolomite reflections consistent with cation ordering. By employing linear
13 regressions for cell refinement as per Turpin, Nader, & Kohler (2012), we ascertain a moderate

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1 similar calcian stoichiometry in dolomite (ca. 51 ± 0.05 wt. % Ca) at the PTB (Fig. 7A'). These
 2 findings, along with the assessed ratios of background-subtracted intensities from the dolomite
 3 015 and 110 reflections (0.546 and 0.609, respectively), imply a slightly higher degree of
 4 crystallinity in the Triassic dolomite compared to the Permian (Fig. 7A-A'). A SEM
 5 backscattered petrography examination further discriminated the PTB samples at bed 37. The
 6 Triassic dolomite rhombs, sized between 40 to 50 μm , presented limited textural preservation
 7 and compositional zonation, contrasting with the compositionally homogeneous and fabric-
 8 preserving nature of the Permian dolomitic beds, which contained well-preserved foraminifera
 9 tests (Fig. 7B-B'). These mineralogical differences highlight the evolution of dolomite
 10 crystallinity and composition across the PTB in the studied section.

11
 12 **Figure 7.** XRD diffraction and backscattered SEM petrography of dolomite at the PTB, Brušane-Sy section. (A)
 13 Diffractograms show b-type reflections indicating cation ordering in Permian (Sy-37x) and Triassic (Sy-37)
 14 samples, with stoichiometry highlighted in inset (A') as slightly calcian, ca. 51 wt. CaCO_3 . The ratio of dolomite
 15 reflections (015:110, Goldschmidt & Graph) is 0.546, and 0.609, respectively, which suggests enhanced Triassic

1 crystallinity. Petrographically, Triassic rhombs (40-50 μm) exhibit limited textural preservation, and often zonation;
2 Permian dolomicrite (B') is homogenous and retains delicate features like foraminifera tests.

3

4 **Biostratigraphy**

5 A detailed biostratigraphic examination confirms the Permian-Triassic boundary at bed 37 (Fig.
6 3). In the lower part of Sy-37x, there is an abundance of foraminifers, among them *Hemigordius*
7 *komiricensis* (Nestell, Sudar, Jovanović & Kolar-Jurkovšek, 2009), *H. sp. 1*, *Midiella sp.*,
8 *Neodiscus sp.*, *Agathammina sp.*, *Geinitzina taurica* (Sellier de Civrieux & Dessauvagie, 1965),
9 *Pachyphloia sp.*, *Dagmarita sp.*, *Rectostipulina quadrata* (Jenny-Deshusses, 1985), *Ammodiscus*
10 *kalhori* (Bronnimann, Zaninetti & Bozorgnia, 1972), and the fusulinid *Staffella sp.*, all of which
11 point to a Late Permian age for the lower part of bed 37 (Appendix A1). Conversely, the upper
12 part of bed 37 (sample Sy-37) lacks foraminifers but features the first appearance of the
13 conodont *Hindeodus parvus* (Kozur & Pjatakova, 1976), which coexisted with *H. pisai* (Perri &
14 Farabegoli, 2003) and *H. typicalis* (Sweet, 1970) (Appendix A2). The conodont faunal
15 assemblage of Sy-37 corresponds to the *H. parvus* Zone or the lower part of the *Isarcicella*
16 *staeschei* Zone of the GSSP Meishan D section, considered as the base of the Triassic (Yin *et al.*,
17 2001; Jiang *et al.*, 2007). Sy-38 yields only *H. praeparvus* which normally ranges from upper
18 most Permian to lower most Triassic (e.g., Jiang *et al.*, 2007). In consequence, the Permian–
19 Triassic boundary can be confidently placed at bed 37 by the first appearance datum of
20 *Hindeodus parvus* at the top of the Brušane-Sy section, (i.e., our sample Sy-37) and the
21 extinction level (EPME) shortly below, and above sample Sy-37x (Fig. 3).

22 **Isotopic $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{carb}}$, and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ data of the Brušane-Sy section**

23 From the base of the section, the samples show negative $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ values ranging from -2.9 to -1.5
24 ‰ (Fig. 8). From 10 m (Sy-6) upwards, these negative values transition to a slightly positive

1 range, with the highest positive value of +2.3 ‰ being situated at 46 m from the base of the
2 section (sample Sy-27a). The values decrease again to a local minimum of +0.5 ‰ at 59 m and
3 show a second smaller positive excursion, with the most positive values +1.9 ‰ in bed 35 (66 m
4 above the base of the section). The values then decrease to ca. 1.2 ‰ in bed 37 and increase
5 slightly to 1.4‰ in Sy-39.

6 The $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{carb}}$ values are positive (0.0 to 0.6 ‰) in the first 5 meters. Then they vary
7 between 0.0 and -1.0 ‰ up to 55 m of the section. They decrease down to -3.0‰ at the top of the
8 section (Sy-39). The $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values show no correlation with $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$.

9 The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ isotope values in the Brušane-Sy section correspond closely with Upper
10 Permian values reported for carbonates at the Rizvanuša locality in the Velebit Mts. (Fio *et al.*,
11 2010). However, in the Rizvanuša section a slightly stronger decline (ca. 2 ‰) was observed at
12 the PTB. The negative excursion at the uppermost part exhibits a relatively modest amplitude of
13 about 0.7 ‰, in comparison to the typical magnitudes documented at the Permian-Triassic (PT)
14 boundary (Baud *et al.*, 1989; Korte & Kozur, 2010; Schobben *et al.*, 2017; Dal Corso *et al.*,
15 2022). Although moderated, it is still present. The apex of the negative excursion between 55 m
16 and 60 m in the section could either represent a local effect or a negative excursion sometimes
17 reported during the late Wuchiapingian (e.g. Richoz *et al.*, 2010; Shen *et al.*, 2013; Bagherpour
18 *et al.*, 2019). Interestingly, stable $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ isotope analyses of organic matter of samples from bed
19 37, bearing the contact between the fine-crystalline (Late Permian) and medium crystalline
20 (Early Triassic) dolostones, reveal $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ values of -26.4 ± 0.2 ‰ for the uppermost Permian,
21 and -31.1 ± 0.1 ‰ for the lowermost Triassic part of the bed. The magnitude of this apparent
22 excursion, ca. 4.6 ‰, is significantly higher than the 0.5 ‰ $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ excursion reported by Fio *et*

- 1 *al.* (2010) when comparing average Late Permian vs. average earliest Triassic organic matter
- 2 values in the PTB bearing strat.

1

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1 **Figure 8.** The recorded Brušane-Sy section with $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ curves.

2 **DISCUSSION**

3 **Depositional environment of the Late Permian Velebit Formation and regional correlation**

4 The dolostone-dominated Velebit Fm. illustrates a depositional setting of a low-energy platform
5 interior (lagoonal subtidal) to peritidal margins (intertidal to supratidal). Representative of an
6 overall shallow-water deposition on an isolated platform, this carbonate system had
7 accumulation rates that kept up with a generally transgressive sea-level. Indeed, the continuous
8 sedimentary sequence is comprised of several shallowing upward cycles. The sequence is
9 notably devoid of terrigenous material which further supports the isolated carbonate platform
10 model (Aljinović *et al.*, 2008; Aljinović & Isozaki, 2010). The presence of foraminifers
11 belonging to the order Hemigordiopsida points to an extremely shallow environment and the
12 absence of conodonts in most of the succession strengthens this interpretation. Furthermore, the
13 occurrence of desiccated and fragmented mud, laminae with cryptomicrobial features, alongside
14 tepee structures, underscores the development of peritidal depositional sub-environments at the
15 perimeter of the isolated carbonate platform.

16 Within the depositional framework described above, early dolomitization appears as a
17 plausible outcome conventionally associated with continued oversaturation, under recurrent
18 evaporite conditions in an arid climate (Sun *et al.*, 2012). Mineral authigenesis in this setting was
19 significantly influenced by microbial activity and salinity changes. It is interesting to note that
20 based on analogous skeletal fragments of various invertebrates, the Upper Permian white
21 dolostone observed in the Brušane-Sy section has been correlated with the Upper Permian
22 Bellerophon Formation encountered in the Slovenian segment of the External Dinarides and the
23 Southern Alps (Kolar-Jurkovšek *et al.*, 2011; 2017, Dolenc *et al.*, 2001; 2004; Sremac, 2005;
24 Farabegoli *et al.*, 2007; Brandner *et al.*, 2012). Yet, contrasting to the limestone-dominated

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1 nature of the Bellerophon Fm. indicative of deposition in back reef lagoons of a shallow ramp,
2 the dolomite-rich Velebit Fm. reflects deposition on an isolated carbonate platform exposed to
3 distinct hydro(bio)geochemical controls. Beyond their disparate carbonate mineralogy, a major
4 difference between the two formations is the conspicuous presence of microbial deposits within
5 the Velebit Fm., which is a feature not reported within the Bellerophon Fm.

6 **Unraveling shallow marine paleoenvironmental transitions at the Permian-Triassic**
7 **boundary at the Brušane-Sy section of the Velebit Formation**

8 The Brušane-Sy section records paleoenvironmental shifts around the PTB, documenting the
9 interplay between major global events and local sedimentological processes. For instance, during
10 the Late Permian, extending into the PTB interval, a marked regression happened, which is
11 portrayed as critical to explain some of the paleoenvironmental changes during that time (Newell
12 1967; Halam & Wignall 1999; Yin *et al.*, 2007; Wu *et al.*, 2010). This long-term regression,
13 however, does not appear to be recorded in the Brušane-Sy section. Instead, several smaller-scale
14 shallowing upward cycles were observed within the Upper Permian interval. These cycles
15 present diagenetic features specific of the exposure to vadose zone diagenesis that point to
16 episodes of supratidal exposure. The recorded depositional dynamics describe the response of an
17 isolated carbonate buildup during a highstand affected by superimposed high-frequency
18 environmental changes (Kendall & Tucker, 2010) rather than during a major regression. The
19 accelerated regression seen in many places correlative to the EPME (Halam & Wignall 1999;
20 Yin *et al.*, 2007) is not seen in Brušane-Sy. Indeed, no karstification, marked dissolution or even
21 hardground is seen in bed 37.

22 After the Upper Permian depositional trend, a general transgression marked the
23 deposition at the beginning of the Early Triassic (Halam & Wignall, 1999). The presence of

1 *Hindeodus parvus* highlights the initiation of this transgressive phase just after the EPME.
2 Indeed, the genera *Hindeodus* maintained a well-defined environmental niche during the
3 transition (see Lai *et al.*, 2001), inhabiting similar subtidal shallow-water depths both during the
4 Late Permian and Early Triassic (Sun *et al.*, 2012; Joachimski *et al.*, 2012). Its appearance thus
5 provides a clear indication of a slightly deeper water-depth during the Early Triassic, but within
6 an overall shallow-water environment.

7 No break in sedimentation during the transition from Late Permian depositional trend to
8 the following transgressive state after the EPME is recorded at the Brušane-Sy section. This
9 continued sedimentation could be explained by the resilience of the pre-established microbial
10 carbonate factory which persisted throughout the Late Permian perturbations and prevailed
11 towards the Early Triassic. Microbial carbonate production was less affected by the EPME as its
12 bioclastic counterparts seen in the other parts of the platform environment. This well-established
13 microbial carbonate factory was capable of keeping-up with sea-level rise, thus minimizing
14 significant environmental shifts that can be caused by the transgression. As higher frequency
15 cyclicity passed to be superimposed by a broader lower order transgressive cycle, a range of
16 environmental conditions that are instrumental for pervasive shallow burial-like diagenetic
17 dolomitization developed. Among those condition were likely subtle changes in carbonate
18 mineral saturation controlled by exposure to alkalinity-modulating redox gradients and
19 schizohaline conditions during alterations between marine and mixing-zone diagenetic stages
20 (Petrash *et al.*, 2016, 2021; McCormack *et al.*, 2023).

21 A sedimentary response during the early transgressive stage could be the possible erosion
22 of the rimmed platform margins by high-energy waves and tidal currents (Posamentier, 2002).
23 This scenario could have led to the reworking of the Late Permian peritidal zones. Consequently,

1 the sediments sourced from these zones might have been subjected to wave abrasion, tide ebbs,
2 and storm swells, which could have winnowed away Late Permian, early diagenetic dolomite
3 crystallites into the Early Triassic lagoon. These crystallites could have then served as nucleation
4 sites, promoting dolomite growth as upwelling of carbonate-saturated, alkaline deep waters
5 (Pruss *et al.*, 2004; Woods, 2014) rekindled the carbonate factory within the lagoon. The
6 ooids/microspheres, associated with slightly deeper depositional conditions due to Early Triassic
7 transgressive trends (Horacek *et al.*, 2012; Fio *et al.*, 2010), would have formed in shoal settings
8 and redeposited in the lagoon or they could have been formed also outside the shoals due to high
9 sea water alkalinity (Li *et al.* 2015). Alongside are dolosparitic crystals poorly preserving the
10 primary oolitic fabric.

11 In the broader paleoceanic context of the end-Permian event, the analysis of pyrite
12 framboids, particularly their size, could be insightful. Petrographic analysis reveals that, in
13 general, Late Permian framboids are $\geq 10 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter, hinting at authigenic aggregation in a
14 euxinic-ferruginous chemocline at or below the sediment–water interface (Wilkin *et al.*, 1996;
15 Wignall & Newton, 1998). However, with transgression and upwelling of euxinic deep basinal
16 waters, the chemocline favourable for framboidal pyrite formation would have shifted upwards
17 and establish itself higher within the water column, leading to the formation of smaller framboids
18 ($< 6 \mu\text{m}$) (Wignall & Newton, 1998). Smaller framboids are typically observed in our Early
19 Triassic samples (Fig.6). The transition from a regressive to a transgressive trend is mirrored in
20 the sedimentological evidences from the Velebit Fm. and underscores the complex interplay of
21 eustatic sea-level changes and broader geological events around the PT boundary.

22 **Dolomitization of the Velebit Fm.**

1 The Velebit Fm., as investigated in the Brušane-Sy section, reveals syngenetic to shallow burial
2 dolomitization within a low energy subtidal platform interior and/or in peritidal settings at the
3 margins. The Late Permian dolomitization is fabric-preserving, implying minimal dissolution-
4 reprecipitation and overgrowth. These characteristics suggest limited exposure to the meteoric
5 end member of the mixing zone, and that the dolomitization occurred predominantly under the
6 influence of seawater-derived dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) as per its $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ values.
7 However, evidence has been presented that Late Permian diagenesis might have also been
8 influenced by relatively high frequency short term regressions that subaerially exposed the
9 platform, leading to the development of tepee and geopetal cementation. Primary dolomitization
10 may have also been triggered by ensuing low-range relative sea-level drops (Flügel, 2004).

11 As brackish groundwater with a meteoric influence admixed with partially evaporated
12 seawater, microbial respiration would have acted as an important driver of cementation and
13 replacement by dolomite (Petrash *et al.*, 2021). Upon exposure to meteoric waters,
14 undersaturation of pore fluid prompted the selective dissolution and replacement of metastable
15 very high-Mg calcitic and aragonitic allochems. Once reintroduced to the dolomite oversaturated
16 conditions, the fabric-preserving micro-scale dissolution-recrystallization processes replacement
17 of allochems ensued. The process was coupled with the replacement of aragonitic micrite in the
18 laminar matrix by the dolomite, whereas dolosparite infilled the fenestral void spaces. Our
19 findings of laminated bindstone structure in Late Permian dolostone (Fig. 4B) bolster the idea of
20 microbial influence during Late Permian dolomitization.

21 Changes in salinity that directly influence the dolomitization rates (Hashim *et al.*, 2023) and
22 the upwelling of carbonate-saturated, alkaline deep waters (Pruss *et al.*, 2004) may have played a
23 significant role as well. Limy mud typically undergoes preferential dolomitization, with

1 abundant nucleation sites leading to fine-grained dolomite replacement but preserving the
2 sedimentary texture and microstructural features of allochems. In terms of mineralogy, high Mg-
3 calcite grains (abundantly found in algae and foraminifers within our samples) present fabric
4 retentive primary fabric (Fig. 7B'). These controlling factors significantly influenced the
5 dolomitization of the Late Permian limestone precursor in the Brušane-Sy section, making the
6 interpretation of the retention of the primary fabric upon early dolomitization plausible (Tucker
7 & Wright, 1990, Mueller *et al.*, 2020). Hence, the primary microcrystalline texture, with crystals
8 smaller than 2 μm (Fig. 7B), strongly supports the notion of syngenetic dolomite formation in the
9 Late Permian strata of the Brušane-Sy section.

10 The overlying Early Triassic dolostone of the Velebit Fm, in contrast, exhibits poor
11 preservation of primary structures (ooids/microspheres, intraclasts) and relatively coarse
12 hypidiotopic/idiotopic mosaics of dolomite rhombs that are more crystalline (Fig. 7A). The shift
13 from fine-crystalline (Permian) to medium/coarse-crystalline (Triassic) textures, evident from the
14 top part of bed 37 onwards in the Triassic dolostone, points to a change in dolomitization
15 mechanisms, linked to broader paleoenvironmental shifts around the PTB. This change can be
16 related to different, not mutually exclusive, mechanisms: (i) redeposition of loose carbonate
17 crystalline detrital grains (Hips & Haas, 2006 and see above), and (ii) shallow burial diagenetic
18 dolomitization involving sources of isotopically contrasting fluids (Petrash *et al.*, 2017, their fig
19 7).

20 The redeposition scenario, aligns with Hips & Haas (2006) and Kolar-Jurkovšek *et al.*
21 (2017) observations that peculiar seawater chemistry during the PTB interval potentially enabled
22 precipitation of aragonite/high Mg calcite detrital groundmass prone to redeposition within the
23 carbonate environment. The redeposited crystals could have behaved as detrital seeds that upon

1 re-sedimentation promoted Early Triassic medium/coarse-crystalline dolomite growth. These
2 crystals, carrying the Permian isotope signal, would later grow in a sediment buffered pore-water
3 system leading to minor changes in the stratigraphic bulk rock $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ curve at the PTB of the
4 Brušane-Sy section. The described process can explain the observed smaller amplitude of the
5 negative excursion, in comparison to other PTB sections.

6 The second dolomitization mechanism interpretation assumes a diagenetic dolomitization
7 front involving isotopically contrasting porewater DIC (Petraš *et al.*, 2017, their fig. 7).
8 Accordingly, the lack of the pronounced $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ excursion at the PTB at Brušane-Sy section can
9 be attributed to alternate admixture of a contrasting source of dissolved inorganic carbon. This
10 process would have been modulated by environmental variables as described by Petraš *et al.*
11 (2021). In this context, the dolomite directly overlying the PTB could be linked to the mass
12 extinction event, producing large amount of buried organic matter. The decline in metazoan
13 populations allowed thick microbial mats to thrive in shallow photic zones bracketing coastal
14 PTB zones (Lehrmann *et al.*, 2001; 2012; 2015; Baud *et al.*, 2005; 2012; Richoz *et al.*, 2010;
15 Kershaw *et al.*, 2011; Leda *et al.*, 2014; Foster *et al.*, 2019). During early diagenesis, these
16 remnant microbial mats influenced dolomite crystal growth via extensive degradation of buried
17 organic matter under substantial methane generation conditions. As Permian methanogenic pore
18 waters enriched in ^{13}C -DIC admixed with ^{13}C -depleted Triassic seawater DIC, further
19 dolomitization proceeded without significantly altering the stratigraphic $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ profile.
20 Interestingly, however, it was noticed that $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ values exhibit a clear shift from -26.4‰ in the
21 Late Permian (microcrystalline dolomite) towards -31.1‰ in the Early Triassic (medium
22 crystalline dolomite). This shift suggests that the C isotope signal of the organic matter better
23 recorded the PTB perturbation more markedly than the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ values in dolostone of the

1 Brušane-Sy section. Determining the prevailing hypothesis would require carefully evaluating
2 whether contrasting C isotope signatures were preserved in multigenic crystals at the relatively
3 coarser Earlier Triassic dolomite.

4

5 CONCLUSION

6 In the Permian, the Velebit Mountains area represents deposition on an isolated carbonate
7 platform. Microfacies and petrographic features of the rocks investigated in the Brušane-Sy
8 section represent deposition in the subtidal zone of a shallow lagoon (dolowackestone and
9 dolopackstone) and on its edge (dolomudstone) in the intertidal/supratidal conditions.

10 A tentative position of the Permian-Triassic boundary was proposed for the succession of the
11 Late Permian and Early Triassic dolostone at the Brušane-Sy section in the middle of bed 37
12 (69.5 m from the base of the section). The boundary line was traced just below a small negative
13 $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ excursion of ~ 0.7 ‰. The main criteria to propose the boundary are: 1) The abrupt
14 disappearance of the abundant Late Permian fossils, especially foraminifers (the last findings of
15 the Late Permian fusulinids of the genus *Staffella* in the sample Sy-37x in the lower part of bed
16 37); 2) Lack of fossils in the sample Sy-37 (the upper part of bed 37) characterizes the earliest
17 Triassic deposition; 3) The recovered conodont species *Hindeodus parvus* (in the sample Sy-37)
18 unambiguously prove its Early Triassic age.

19 Microfacies characteristics, especially the dolomite microcrystalline structure and well-
20 preserved features of former limestone fabric, indicate primary, syngenetic dolomitization of
21 Late Permian rocks related to microbial activities that enhanced dolomitization processes. These
22 conditions changed around the PT boundary. The Early Triassic dolostone (samples Sy-37 and
23 Sy-38) with medium- to coarse-crystalline texture can be explained by two different

1 dolomitization processes: 1) The Early Triassic transgression favoured redeposition of
2 aragonite/high Mg-calcite loose crystals that served as precursors for medium/coarse dolomite
3 crystal growth; 2) dolomitization in the early diagenesis condition influenced by mixing of
4 isotopically contrasting DIC fluids under substantial methane generation due to the mass
5 extinction.

6 The absence of the expected negative $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ isotope excursion at the PTB in the Brušane-Sy
7 section suggests the influence of diagenetic processes, particularly dolomitization, under unique
8 PTB conditions. The minimal change in $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ values ($\sim 0.7\text{‰}$) could be a result of either the
9 redeposition of precursor carbonate materials in a sediment-buffered system or the result of
10 fabric-destructive dolomitization during early diagenesis involving isotopically diverse sources
11 of DIC, including methanogenically derived CO_2 . Both scenarios imply that the original carbon
12 isotopic signature was altered during diagenesis, masking the primary signal. To ascertain the
13 dominant process, it is essential to evaluate the preservation of contrasting carbon isotope
14 signatures in the coarser Early Triassic dolomite. This examination will help determine whether
15 the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ values reflect a sediment-buffered or a fluid-buffered system, thereby shedding light
16 on the diagenetic history of the PTB in this section.

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17 **Supporting Information**

18 **Appendix A1.** Supplemental Paleontological Information for the Elucidation of the PTB
19 Boundary at Brušane-Sy Section.

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Supplemental Data for:

Traversing the Permian-Triassic threshold: Insights from the dolomite of the Velebit Mountains, External Dinarides, Croatia

DUNJA ALJINOVIĆ, SYLVAIN RICHOSZ, DUJE SMIRČIĆ, YANLONG CHEN, GALINA

NESTELL, IVAN JAZVAC and DANIEL A. PETRASH

Appendix A. Supplementary Plate A1

1 Algae and foraminifers investigated in the Brušane-Sy section, Croatia. **1-4**, Acanthomorphic
2 (spinose) acritarchs (possibly *Micrhystridium* sp.). **5-6**, Sphaeromorphic acritarchs or
3 calcispheres. **7**, *Tuberitina?* sp. **8**, *Hyperammina deformis* (Bérczi-Makk, 1987). **9**, *Ammodiscus*
4 *kalhori* (Brönnimann, Zaninetti and Bozorgnia, 1972). **10-11**, *Pseudospira* ex gr.
5 *specialisaeformis* (Lin, Li and Sun, 1990). **12**, *Dagmarita?* sp. **13**, *Globivalvulina vonderschmitti*
6 Reichel, 1946. **14**, *Globivalvulina* sp. **15**, *Hemigordius* cf. *komiricensis* Nestell, Sudar, Jovanović
7 and Kolar-Jurkovšek, 2009. **16**, *Glomomidiellopsis* sp. 1. **17**, *Neodiscus* sp. **18**, *Hemigordius* sp.
8 **19**, *Glomomidiellopsis* sp. 2. **20**, *Agathammina* sp. **21**, *Rectostipulina quadrata* Jenny-Deshusses,
9 1985. **22**, *Agathammina* cf. *psebaensis* Pronina-Nestell in Pronina, Nestell and Nestell, 2001. **23**,
10 *Langella* sp. **24**, *Protonodosaria mirabilis caucasica* (K. Miklukho-Maklay, 1954). **25**,
11 *Dentalina* sp. **26**, *Nodosaria* sp. 1. **27**, *Nodosaria* sp. 2. **28**, *Pachyphloia* sp. 29-31, *Staffella?* sp.
12 Scale bar is 100 µm.

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1 Appendix A. Supplementary Plate A2

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4 SEM microphotographs of conodonts from the Brušane-Sy section, Croatia. **1**, *Hindeodus pisai*
5 (Perri and Farabegoli, 2003). **2–4**, *Hindeodus typicalis* (Sweet, 1970). **5**, *Hindeodus parvus*
6 (Kozur & Pjatakova, 1976). **6–7**, *Hindeodus cf. praeparvus* (Kozur). Note that 1-5 recovered
7 from sample Sy-37; 6-7 from sample Sy-38. a lateral view; b, lower view. Scale bar is 200 µm.

8 **References to Appendix A**

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